

Commodification of News and Social Media as Threats to Status Conferral Role of Mass Media in Nigeria

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Abstract

The commodification of news which is the infamous commercialisation of news coverage has been critically engaged as a major factor that robs the mass media of its independence in exploring status conferral to the ultimate good of the society. The strengths, weaknesses and application of the Status Conferral Theory propounded in 1948 by Paul Lazarsfeld and Robert Merton as an explainer of the role the mass media plays in the society through news coverage have been discussed with emphasis on the Nigerian paradigm. With the use of Library Research method, the study has been able to establish how the emergence and popularity of the social media have also encroached on the status conferral role of the mainstream media. Specific recommendations have been made on how the narrative can be reversed to reposition the mass media as indispensable social institutions.

Introduction

The effects of the mass media on the audience continue to be a subject of scholarly debate and research leading to postulation of different theories to explain the phenomenon. From the formulation of the first widely recognised mass communication theory of Magic Bullet or Hypodermic Needle Theory in 1927 by Harold Lasswell, there is a continuous discourse that has deepened and expanded knowledge in this regard in nearly a century. This is such that a number of scholars have narrowed down their research works and theories to the specific ways in which the mass media is deployed to influence the audience. One of such is the Status Conferral Theory (SCT) propounded by Paul Lazarsfeld and Robert Merton in 1948 who were explaining the functions and power of the mass media.

According to Akene (1992), the traditional roles assigned to the mass media include informing, educating and entertaining. However, Smith (2016) explains that the Status Conferral

Theory came about as Lazarsfeld and Merton explained the functions and power that the mass media has in the society which includes the ability to flood the public space with so much information from anywhere at any given time and about any subject matter and the ability to make a topic seem like the most pressing issue to date. To Omoera & Guanah (2022), Status Conferral Theory indicates that media coverage singles out and elevates the covered person or organisation as important enough from the mass and that one's behaviour and opinions are significant and sufficient enough to demand media attention.

Instructively, not a few scholars have linked Status Conferral Theory to the Agenda Setting Theory ascribed to Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw, who proposed it in 1972 after their research of the 1968 American Presidential election on how the mass media covered the issues that voters in Chapel Hill in North Carolina thought were most important (Aigbefoh, Orah and Asemah, 2024). According to Sanusi, Okunade, Ogungbamigbe & Anieudo (2014), the Status Conferral Theory is a concept under the umbrella of the Agenda Setting Theory and it was propounded by Paul Lazarsfeld and Robert Merton in 1948, referring to the amount of attention given to individuals by the media. For Bellos & Sanusi (2022), "The powerful effects of the media suggest that the media, under the Status Conferral Theory, has the power to confer status on things and persons due to increased or focused coverage on such persons which by the agenda-setting theory of the mass media, gives people what to think about and inadvertently confers celebrity status on such persons".

However, in Kur & Nyekwere (2015), "one of the most disturbing issues in the Nigeria mass media industry is the commercialisation of news. This is a practice whereby media organisations raise revenue to sustain their operations by charging fees for news reports they should normally carry free. This unethical practice is the case in virtually all television and radio

stations in Nigeria. It is a serious threat to freedom of expression”. Adaja (2011) has traced this commodification of news in Nigeria to the deregulation of the broadcast industry in 1992 when the military government of General Ibrahim Babangida promulgated Decree No. 38 in that year to establish the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC). The deregulation was within the policy direction of the government, which embraced and supported World Bank and IMF-driven privatisation of public enterprises on debtor nations. Onoja (2009) explains that in 1988 the public broadcasters, namely, the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA) and Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria (FRCN) were listed among some of the federal government agencies that were to be partially commercialised and this was implemented in July 1992. In the words of Kur & Nyekwere (2015), “from this moment, the concept “Let Them Pay” (LTP) became very alive in broadcast stations. The concept of commercial news also became popular. Though this practice is against provisions of the NBC Code, it has gained momentum, with the regulatory agencies unable to stop it”. Unfortunately, this practice has gradually caught up with the print media that treats such as special reports or what they popularly call “supplements”. The problem this study seeks to investigate is to find out the extent to which this commercialisation or commodification of news and the growing popularity of the social media affect the status conferral function of the mass media in Nigeria.

Review of Status Conferral Theory

The Status Conferral Theory propounded in 1948 by Paul Lazarsfeld and Robert Merton assumes that by often featuring people in the mass media, people are given status and according to Chukwu & Anavberokhai (2024), this demonstrates that individuals prefer to view some persons as significant members of society the more the mass media highlights and portrays them. This is because the mass media cannot feature individuals irrelevant to society. The theory holds that the

mass media gives status and legitimacy to individuals, ideas, and organisations and emphasises those seen as prominent figures in society, as well as increases their popularity. The theorists had argued further that being noticed by the media is a sign of success, significant enough to have been chosen out of the vast, faceless multitudes and significant enough for one's actions and thoughts to merit public attention thereby elevating their social stature and bestowing prestige upon them.

Asabor (2020) says that getting mass media attention, especially from respected media outlets, gives the public an impression that a person or event is important and deserving of consideration. This obviously elicits organised social action, because the mass media has legitimised the person or event by giving its support. Chukwu & Anavberokhai (2024) point to the consensus among scholars that status-conferral function of the media is achieved by exposing individuals to large audiences for one good reason or the other, to make them appear important or esteemed. In agreement, Ate & Sunday (2009) assert that the mass media has the power to make instant celebrities of hitherto unknown persons, either for good or bad. In Nigeria, people who are well connected are looked up to as opinion leaders and the function of status conferral in the country comes from being the subject of the subject of news reports.

It is important to understand that the concept of Status Conferral Theory was propounded within the context of the sociology of mass communication. The two theorists, Paul Felix Lazarsfeld and Robert Merton who both became professors were sociologists at the Columbia University in the United States. While Professor Lazarsfeld who was born on February 13, 1901 was an Austrian-American sociologist and mathematician, Professor Robert King Merton, originally born as Meyer Robert Schkolnick on January 4, 1910 as an American who founded the Sociology of Science for which he was awarded the National Medal of Science in 1994 for his contributions to the field. Both academics were appointed as new faculty members in the

Department of Sociology of the Columbia University in 1941 and that was the beginning of their working together on the first day they met each other. Their meeting day was indeed dramatic as both men abandoned their wives and uneaten dinner when Merton visited Lazarsfeld's Manhattan apartment on the Saturday evening of November 23, 1941. Lazarsfeld had just been asked by the U.S government's Office of New Facts and Figures to evaluate a radio programme and both men left immediately to the radio studio, to record the responses of listeners, and in the ensuing interviews they conducted. This was believed to be the start of the "focused group interview", or what is today known as Focus Group Discussion (FGD) in qualitative research method. The rest is history but Professor Lazarsfeld died on August 30, 1976 while Professor Merton died on February 23, 2003.

From the background provided above, it is clear that the theorists as sociologists were using the prism of the social system in any given society where the mass media functions as a social institution within the organised structure of the community and the relationship between the different peoples and groups including opinion leaders, prime movers, the independents, dissidents and the networks which have been defined by Cutlip, Centre & Brown (1985) as cited in Ajala (2000). Indeed, the role of the mass media in shaping public opinion, framing narratives, and conferring status to individuals, ideas, and issues cannot be overstated. Though the Status Conferral Theory is situated within the context of social institutions, it ignores the fact that beyond the mass media, structures such as the legal system, education, and political organisations also contribute to the conferral of status.

Political leaders or institutions may designate individuals as leaders or experts in their field, effectively shaping the social hierarchy. Similarly, universities or intellectual platforms may deem certain ideas or scholars worthy of attention, impacting public perception of their significance. Iredia (2012) reminds us about the counter school of thought, which posits that the media alone can neither account for the direction of public opinion, attitudes and conduct nor are they the only cause of crime, violence, or other social observable phenomena. Akpan (1985) agrees that there are factors which facilitate the overwhelming power of the media that includes status conferrals.

Another criticism of the Status Conferral Theory is the tendency to promote and perpetuate social inequality and marginalisation. Chukwu & Anavberokhai, (2024) explain that the media has been described as having the power, capacity, and enormity, to make a previously unknown thing become known. This power is such that a rather unknown personality, issue, or occurrence when covered by the media can suddenly become ubiquitous. Obviously, the application of status conferral often reinforces existing power structures. In many cases, groups that are already marginalised, such as racial minorities or economically disadvantaged communities, may be overlooked or presented in a negative light. As a result, these groups remain less likely to attain social or political power, which further perpetuates cycles of inequality. Most times, this is rooted in the ownership structure of the media organisations leading to certain analysts from a particular section consistently presented, or if their perspectives dominate the coverage of specific issues, it can create a one-sided narrative. This concentration of expert voices can marginalise alternative viewpoints, undermining the diversity of discourse and potentially shaping the public's understanding in a skewed manner that can create or reinforce social inequality, as some individuals or groups are granted more access to opportunities based on these institutional endorsements. The regular feature of individuals ends up giving them the status of important personalities within society and Anaeto, Onabajo & Osifeso (2008) say they get talked about more, after which the audience starts actively seeking out news on such persons or groups due to the initial attention given to these individuals by the media.

Contextual Review

News on any radio or television station for instance is a “Grade A” broadcast. This explains the importance of news in any media organisation including thematic stations. According to Asemah (2009), there is no universally accepted definition of news but in his identifying proximity,

prominence, conflict, timeliness, human interest, unusualness and significance as the factors that determine newsworthiness of an event. “News is the live wire of mass communication industries (Asemah, 2009). It is the account of something that is unusual, odd, out of the ordinary, bothers on human interests and affects larger section of the people”. To Maamaa (2008), news is the account of event that has taken place or that has refused to take place. Bittner (1989) however threw up posers when he wrote that:

We may feel that after reading a newspaper and a news magazine, listening to various radio newscasts throughout the day, and watching a local and national television news program, we have been exposed to all the news that could possibly happen in one day, such is not the case. Reporters are constantly faced with a multitude of stories from which to choose, scores of events to report and a myriad of decisions to make about what should appear in print or on air. Why are some stories chosen and others not? Why do some stories carry pictures and others do not? Why are some stories on the front page or lead a broadcast while others are either buried or do not ever appear?

In Nigeria, media reports revolve mainly around those in power and those who have done one thing or the other that attracted the attention of a large majority of the mass audience (Chukwu & Anavberokhai, 2024). This level of coverage and exposure which eventually leads to the conferral of status whether the individual is deserving or undeserving is what Asabor (2020) calls an advantage that Nigerians, particularly the politicians, have been leveraging on since the emergence of journalism in the country, especially “when they have the ambition to contest for a political position or get appointment at any given dispensation”. Chukwu & Anavberokhai (2024), therefore say that the Status Conferral function of the media in Nigeria provides information about public figures who are mostly considered opinion leaders and decision makers, and also information about events and happenings which the media makes important with status allocation.

However, according to Clare (2004), “the first step in the production of news is in the choice of which events to cover” and the big question you must ask yourself before you approach

any journalist with a story is how relevant is this to their audience”. This may be the ground rules but also agrees that “having explained the process, the next question is whether you can influence it. The answer is yes, to a degree”. One major influencer which news must cover especially in Nigeria is commercialisation of news, infamously known as “Let Them Pay”. Practically, all broadcast stations have advertisement rates that include the cost of covering news stories and whoever can pay gets covered and will fully enjoy the Status Conferral privileges which the media did not deservingly give to him or her but was bought with his or her money.

Bittner (1989) in identifying some of the factors affecting news selection admits that economics plays a crucial role. In his words, “with the exception of non-commercial media, such as campus radio stations or some campus newspapers, most media are commercial, profit-making businesses. Our context is the free-world countries where the majority of media operates as free enterprises. An economic fact of life is that these media must make a profit or go out of business”. In Nigeria however, Section 5.1.4 of the sixth edition of the country’s Broadcasting Code prohibits the commercialisation or selling of news to raise money and improve the financial standing of broadcast stations as this “predisposes a bias in favour of the sponsor”, encourages partisanship and does not give equal access to people to express their views freely even though news is “sacred”. This practice obviously compromises standards and marginalises a majority of those who cannot afford to pay as it does not provide a level playing ground and is against the principle of social justice.

Empirical Review

In his study, “News commercialisation and its implications on media credibility among two selected areas in Nigeria: Abuja and Lagos, Ebuka (2024) adopted the survey research method and deployed Multi-stage sampling techniques to administer 385 questionnaires on residents of Marine

Beach in Lagos State and Gwarimpa in Abuja. Majority of the respondents indicated that they were already familiar with the different news commercialisation strategies used by the mass media which takes away objectivity and believability of news that remains a prerequisite for its status conferral function. The research which explored the Social Responsibility Theory concluded that “the scheme of news commercialisation may continue to occur within the two selected areas if the media do not assign a legal order and proceedings in ensuring that the issue is restrained and make good of a media organisation that follow the ethics of journalism”.

An earlier work by Iheanacho, Okala & Ukpng (2021) on “Journalists' Perception of the Challenges of News Commercialisation and News as Public good”, showed that the continuous growth in news commercialisation negates the ethics of journalism and this is leading to a temporary decline of journalism's expensive but vital watchdog function, which includes its status conferral role in the society. The research made use of the survey research method with questionnaire administered on 389 journalists in Imo State, South-East Nigeria using the census principle. The respondents viewed commercialisation of media as a means of survival in the quest to fulfil their duties even though they agreed that the practice influences news content and news as public good. Based on this, the study in advancing the tenets of Social Responsibility Theory recommended that there should be an improved salary for journalist as this can control the urge to seek personal reward and minimise or eliminate the conditions driving commercialisation of news.

A related study on “Journalists’ perspectives on news commercialisation and its influences on media credibility in journalism practice in Nigeria” by Fadeyi & Suleiman (2023) who also conducted a survey on journalists from 12 media groups but in Osun State, South-West Nigeria looked at “how Nigerian media are becoming more commercialised”. It concluded that the way news is reported does not change much when it becomes more commercial as a result most people

think that making news as commercials hurts the media's credibility and trustworthiness. It emphasises that “unprofessional news commercialisation harms media and journalists” because it “weakens journalistic and media social responsibility” as “paid media deceives the public (as the people believe all contents from the media are objective)”. The research recommends that “people would trust the news more if the Nigeria Union of Journalists (NUJ) and other media groups could work out better pay for journalists”.

Discussion of Social Media and Status Conferral Role

It is obvious that the Status Conferral Theory did not in 1948 contemplate the emergence, popularity and role of the Social Media as seen in the 21st century. According to Bellos & Sanusi (2022), with the advent of social media, it is believed that some of this power of the media has been relinquished to the audience. Other theories in this regard believe that the audiences now have the power to choose how they react to mass media messages”. With the ability of social media platforms to broadcast messages instantaneously, individuals and groups now have the power to confer status in ways that were not previously possible.

Indeed, in the digital era, social media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, X, and TikTok among others serve as new horizons for status conferral. Today, there are social media influencers even comedy skit producers who are not created by the mainstream media with celebrities, and online communities now having the power to confer status with a simple like, share, or comment. In fact, effective use of the social media does not only confer status but it has proven to create wealth thereby economically elevating the status of the beneficiaries including cross dressers. For instance, music artists and movie producers no longer have to wait for the mainstream media to promote them and their works amid the piracy crisis but they now make good money with number of views and streaming of their contents online.

Methodology

This study adopted the qualitative research approach using Library Research design to rely on data from secondary materials such as books, articles in book chapters and journals, magazines, newspapers and website publications. According to Asemah (2020), the implication is that “this work was borne out of consultations of both empirical and theoretical studies carried out by scholars in this field of study” to arrive at a position of discourse, and in the words of Omoha (2020) “come out with valid findings”.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The conclusion of this study is that the notion of an overwhelming media power including the responsibility for status conferral remains a strong public perception despite the fact that the social media in particular has greatly encroached on this territory. This is more so as the mass media is often times needed to validate what happens on the social media. Consequently, the research recommends that:

- a) Media organisations should ensure that they establish and maintain strong social media presence to have a footprint that can make them also participate or determine the trending issues online. This will make the mass media a force that cannot be ignored despite the emergence of the New Media which proponents of the Status Conferral Theory did not contemplate but has become a reality.
- b) To reduce over-dependence on advertisements and guarantee editorial independence which will allow media organisations to objectively perform their functions and role in the society, they should brand their platforms and reposition their content to benefit handsomely from the legitimate monetisation of their online services. These include their websites and social media handles which will attract revenue to adequately fund their

operations and make profit. This will help them overcome the operational challenges that usually force most of them into commercialisation of news as a means of survival. And as their online revenue earnings improve, the welfare of their workers including salaries and other entitlements should be increased and given priority for better service delivery.

- c) Media organisations in their news content need to make deliberate efforts to reflect most if not all shades of opinion within the societies in which they operate to help shape the way the public perceives complex topics. This will address concerns over media's perpetuation of social inequalities and marginalisation especially of minorities, gender, youths or economically disadvantaged communities through the selective nature of status conferral which can lead to biases in the framing of public discourse.

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